

Web Accessibility Standards in Uzbekistan: A Review of Current Practices

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ABSTRACT:

As the internet has become the essential part of our daily life, many people are still struggling to get access to the information on the Internet, and web accessibility exists to cease this type of problems. Web accessibility is significant term in today's IT world since it ensures that everyone, including those with disabilities, have a proper access to the information on the Web. The problem with proper access to the Web got very popular in Uzbekistan due to its past when government did not focus and lagged behind in development of the Internet. However, Uzbekistan has been demonstrating an impressive blooming of new strategies and plans to tackle the problem with web accessibility for a long time. The aim of this paper delves into analyzing current practices of web accessibility with challenges and barriers of properly employing web accessibility in Uzbekistan by utilizing mixed-methods approach.

Keywords: accessibility, web accessibility, people with disabilities, internet, web, access to information, Uzbekistan.

Suggested Citation: M. Islomov, "Web Accessibility Standards in Uzbekistan: A Review of Current Practices," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(6), pp. 211-217, Nov-Dec 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(6\).22](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(6).22)

INTRODUCTION

As the 21st century is called the age of information technology, the use of the Internet has been rapidly spreading to different aspects of people's lives, such as education, news, communication, entertainment, health care, work and information access, especially in the late 2010s due to COVID-19 (Figure 1). It is a must for governments to make web services - which made the lives of many people easier by solving everyday problems, e.g. much time and long- waiting queues, to get services - available for every sector of the population without any exceptions including those with disabilities in order to keep everyone and their opportunities equal.

To understand what web accessibility is, we need to know about the connotation of accessibility in this context. The Web is designed with the aim that it would work and be accessible for all people equally in spite of their hardware, software, location, language, nation or ability. Therefore, many people with certain types of disabilities whether they are permanent or temporary feel that the barriers, such as communication and interaction, which they encounter in the real life are removed. However, when websites, applications, technologies, or tools are badly designed, they can create barriers that exclude people from using the Web. Access to information and communications technologies, including the Web, is defined as a basic human right in the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN CRPD). "The power of the Web is in its universality. Access by everyone regardless of disability is an essential aspect." (Tim Berners-Lee, W3C Director and inventor of the World Wide Web) [13,14].

Figure1. Internet Use Timeline (1990-2024)

Web accessibility is a broad term that applies to transforming websites and web-based applications so that they are accessible to people with disabilities. The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) provide a framework for making web content more accessible to people with a wide range of abilities and disabilities. These guidelines are based on four key principles, often summarized as POUR, each crucial for creating a universally accessible web [13,14].

- Perceivability
- Operability
- Understandability
- Robustness

Web accessibility can also benefit people without permanent disabilities [15].

For Example:

- people using mobile phones, smart watches, smart TVs, and other devices with small screens, different input modes, etc.;
- older people with changing abilities due to ageing;
- people with “temporary disabilities” such as a broken arm or lost glasses;
- people with “situational limitations” such as in bright sunlight or in an environment where they cannot listen to audio;
- people using a slow Internet connection, or who have limited or expensive bandwidth.

Web accessibility is an essential aspect of digital inclusion that holds particular importance for Uzbekistan, a nation rapidly embracing technology and digital transformation. Internet penetration in Uzbekistan increased sharply in 2012, reaching a reported 36.5 percent of the population, or about 11 million Internet users, according to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU). The Uzbek Agency for Communications and Informatization reports that as of March 19, 2012, the figure had reached 9.1 million [16].

The number of Internet users in Uzbekistan has exceeded 31 million, of which 29.5 million are mobile Internet users, said the head of the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications, Sherzod Shermatov (2022). As of 2022, 845.3 thousand people, or 2.3% of the total population, were officially recognized as people with disabilities. People with disabilities tend to have less access to information than people without disabilities. Data from a 2019 study shows that the proportion of people with disabilities who believe they have full access to the information they need is 54%, compared to 70% for people without disabilities. As the country continues to develop its online presence and e-services, ensuring that all citizens, regardless of their abilities or disabilities, can access and navigate the web becomes crucial [17].

A commitment to web accessibility enhances overall user experience by not only targeting the audience with disabilities, but also elderly people, those with temporary diseases and many others.

Uzbekistan positions itself as a growing hub for technology in Central Asia, and investment in web accessibility showcases that Uzbekistan is committed to innovation and modernization.

This study will explore the current state of web accessibility in Uzbekistan, and it will assess the implementation of web accessibility in local websites. The understanding of current practices in web accessibility in Uzbekistan is provide in this article by discussing some common challenges and reasons of developer or companies not prioritizing accessibility.

LITERATURE REVIEW

For developing countries and for Uzbekistan, in particular, digital transformation has a potential to further modernize society and integrate national economy into the global processes, – says Farrukh Khakimov, Head of Department at the Development Strategy Center. – In this vein, in the framework of the ongoing reforms and in the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for the coming five years special attention is being paid to digitalization of major spheres and to build a true information society in the country (Diplomat magazine 2022.04.24) [12].

The manual was developed by IT-Academy LLC with the support of the Regional Office of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) for the CIS Region and the Association of Disabled People of Uzbekistan. They made recommendations for Internet users, including those with disabilities. They stated “The guidelines can be used to improve the accessibility of websites of government agencies, businesses, social services, universities and other organizations aimed at creating inclusive web content for a wide range of users” [10].

There is no need to reinvent the wheel to ensure digital accessibility. A global standard has been developed to ensure web content accessibility for people with disabilities — Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.2. This guide includes detailed recommendations to make websites and applications more accessible to users with various types of disabilities, such as visual impairment, hearing impairment, physical limitations, speech impairment, cognitive and neurological impairment. Unfortunately, the global standard WCAG 2.2 is not widely used in Uzbekistan and is not recognized at the legislative level [11].

A research article published in June 2024 about “Accelerating the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities in Uzbekistan’s Digital Economy” has mentioned many times about the problem with the inclusion of people with disabilities on the Internet. It analyzed the digital inclusion ecosystem for persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan, the experiences of persons with disabilities, a roadmap to harness the digital opportunity for persons with disabilities and proposed interventions and next steps in the end [6].

METHODOLOGY

Considering various research methods that aim to obtain summarized information about a given topic, the method of choice for this paper is mixed-methods approach by focusing more on getting information from existing websites, as it allows to summarize more reliable data, leading to better interpretation of collected data.

DISCUSSION

Law and Guidelines that exist in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has been a country where equality was considered as one of the most vital laws of the country. In recent years, the government of Uzbekistan has made several important steps in recognizing and addressing a popular but little discussed topic, that is web accessibility, particularly for those with disabilities. There were many novel initiatives, regulations and governmental laws to address web accessibility and digitalization of the country.

The most care and concern for people with disabilities showed The Law on Social Protection of Disabled Persons, which is considered as the core of the laws, regulations and rights of the people with disabilities. The Law on Social Protection of Disabled Persons fundamentally works with people with disabilities to ensure them a life in equal terms with those who do not have any disabilities. Therefore, it makes mandatory for governments, companies and agencies to consider equal accessibility in their services and to the information, including those provided online. In its convention of the rights of persons with disabilities which took effect on 28.07.2021, The Law on Social Protection of Disabled Persons in Article 9, which comply with United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and is about Accessibility, mandate:

“To enable persons with disabilities to live independently and participate fully in all aspects of life, States Parties shall take appropriate measures to ensure to persons with disabilities access, on an equal basis with others, to the physical environment, to transportation, to information and communications, including information and communications technologies and systems, and to other facilities and services open or provided to the public, both in urban and in rural areas.”

And, in second part in f, g and h sections, it wrote:

States Parties shall also take appropriate measures to:

- (f) Promote other appropriate forms of assistance and support to persons with disabilities to ensure their access to information;
- (g) Promote access for persons with disabilities to new information and communications technologies and systems, including the Internet;
- (h) Promote the design, development, production and distribution of accessible information and communications technologies and systems at an early stage, so that these technologies and systems become accessible at minimum cost [7].

Moreover, there was written a legislation about the access to information for people with disabilities on The Law on Social Protection of Disabled Persons' Convention of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Article 21 a, c and d sections, which comply with United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, and it mandates:

States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that persons with disabilities can exercise the right to freedom of expression and opinion, including the freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas on an equal basis with others and through all forms of communication of their choice, as defined in article 2 of the present Convention, including by:

- (a) Providing information intended for the general public to persons with disabilities in accessible formats and technologies appropriate to different kinds of disabilities in a timely manner and without additional cost;
- (b) Urging private entities that provide services to the general public, including through the Internet, to provide information and services in accessible and usable formats for persons with disabilities;
- (d) Encouraging the mass media, including providers of information through the Internet, to make their services accessible to persons with disabilities [7];

Article 2 Definition of “Communication”:

«Communication» includes languages, display of text, Braille, tactile communication, large print, accessible multimedia as well as written, audio, plain-language, human-reader and augmentative

and alternative modes, means and formats of communication, including accessible information and communication technology [7].

The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (hereinafter referred to as the Guidelines) offer numerous recommendations aimed at ensuring greater accessibility of web content. Implementation of these recommendations will make web content accessible to a wider range of users with disabilities, such as visual impairment (blind and visually impaired), hearing impairment (deaf and hard of hearing), musculoskeletal disorders, speech impairments, mental disorders, as well as various combinations of multiple and combined disabilities. In addition, implementation of these recommendations will make the site's web content more accessible to users, regardless of the presence or absence of any limitations.

The criteria for implementing the recommendations are presented in the form of verifiable statements that are not tied to technologies. The Guidelines were developed by IT-Academy LLC with the support of the Regional Office of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) for the CIS Region and the Association of Disabled People of Uzbekistan. The guidelines can be used to improve the accessibility of websites of government agencies, businesses, social services, universities, and other organizations aimed at creating inclusive web content for a wide range of users [10].

Commonly used websites in Uzbekistan and their adherence to accessibility standards. In recent years, Uzbekistan started actively adopting the international web accessibility standards, particularly Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1, and creating websites which comply with those standards and guidelines so as to ensure the accessibility of all people, including those with disabilities and many other limitations.

I chose to focus on the most significant sectors of life in Uzbekistan which are government websites, healthcare services, educational institutions and e-commerce platforms because they are the most used websites in Uzbekistan.

There are several government websites that people usually use for their own purposes, but I chose three of them, that is gov.uz (Government Portal), mfa.uz (Ministry of Foreign Affairs), minfin.uz (Ministry of Finance). There are several things that make these websites accessible for everyone even though they still lack many functions.

For instance:

- these websites provide basic alt text on many pages;
- they use clear and simple language which easy to understand and some of them even have multilingual functions which make the website more readable;
- they use sufficient color contrast between text and background; and many other functions which make the website accessible for everyone.

However, there is still room for improvement since the websites themselves still lack many functions, such as not clear navigation; no text resizing which do not allow users with mobility impairments to access all functionalities without a mouse; and etc., to make these websites more accessible for everyone.

Healthcare service, educational institutions and e-commerce platform websites demonstrate that Uzbekistan has been and still progressing in web accessibility. The reason being that is the compliance with some of the international standards and guidelines of web accessibility as the same in government websites they provide basic alt text for most of the images; useful search functionalities; and some of them provide basic accessibility features for resizing. In the same way as government websites, these websites still lack many functions, such as lack of mobile-friendly features; limited language options; many sites inadequately use headings, complicating navigation; and many others which show us that these websites still need to be improved.

Challenges and Barriers

Lack of Awareness. Even though Uzbekistan has been focusing on adopting web accessibility standard and guidelines, it still hasn't started actively educating developers and businessmen. There are many educational programs in which many developers and businesses take part in, but still those

programs overlook crucial moments in web accessibility, resulting limited or no knowledge in it. The absence of the special educational programs and workshops focused on web accessibility, especially accessibility of people with disabilities; if those problems are not trackled, Uzbekistan will remain in the state where its citizens and residents are not well-aware of web accessibility.

Many businesses focus more on functionality or aesthetics than inclusivity leading to low level of prioritization of web accessibility which makes it more difficult for people with disabilities to have an access to information on the Web.

In Uzbekistan, it is popular to follow on trends which came from other countries; then, localize and adapt it in Uzbekistan. There are many international standards and guidelines which have been adapted and changed to their own convenience in Uzbekistan, leading to misinformation in web accessibility standards and guidelines since local people follow local and better-known information which may slightly or significantly differ from the original.

Technical Constraints of web accessibility in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan is still struggling with limited internet connectivity. Many areas, especially rural areas, in Uzbekistan experience slow or unreliable internet connections, which can be the cause of hindering accessibility of web content.

Uzbekistan's total population was 34.16 million in January 2022. Data show that Uzbekistan's population increased by 457 thousand (+1.4 percent) between 2021 and 2022. 50.1 percent of Uzbekistan's population is female, while 49.9 percent of the population is male. At the start of 2022, 50.5 percent of Uzbekistan's population lived in urban centers, while 49.5 percent lived in rural areas [8].

There were 24.05 million internet users in Uzbekistan in January 2022. Uzbekistan's internet penetration rate stood at 70.4 percent of the total population at the start of 2022. Kepios analysis indicates that internet users in Uzbekistan increased by 321 thousand (+1.4 percent) between 2021 and 2022. For perspective, these user figures reveal that 10.11 million people in Uzbekistan did not use the internet at the start of 2022, meaning that 29.6 percent of the population remained offline at the beginning of the year [8].

Although the statistics are of 2022, the numbers are only increasing and Uzbekistan is improving for the better.

Most of the people in Uzbekistan usually use mobile devices, and most of them do not even have laptops which creates the Mobile-First Dependency problem. And, the only way to access to the internet is via their mobile devices, but there may sometimes occur some problems related to accessibility since mobile platforms do not always support accessibility features effectively.

Even though there is some legislations about web accessibility in Uzbekistan, many people neglect them since the government is not strict enough. Therefore, many significant standards of web accessibility are just ignored among developers and organizations.

CONCLUSION

The Internet has already become one of the most if not the most important part of our life. People use the Internet for various reasons starting from cooking, reading and playing games ending with traveling, studying and communicating. Everyone does not have the same abilities, languages, cultures or ages, so they may lack knowledge or abilities to have an access to the information on the Web. Therefore, to prevent this problem, there is a term called 'web-accessibility' which ensures that everyone has equal opportunities to be able to access to the information. Uzbekistan as many other countries has already started adopting the international standards and guidelines of web accessibility. Many people with disabilities whether they are temporary or permanent had better experiences when accessing the the Internet after those changes. There were seen many tangible results of these adaptations and changes, yet still there are many problems that need to be fixed, and there is definitely a scope for enhancement.

REFERENCES

1. Gazeta.uz, "The number of people with disabilities in Uzbekistan and their rights," available at: <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2023/06/01/disability/>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
2. Gazeta.uz, "Internet in Uzbekistan: Access and development," available at: <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2022/12/15/internet/>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
3. IT-Park Uzbekistan, "A guide on ensuring web content accessibility has been developed," available at: <https://it-park.uz/ru/itpark/news/razrobotano-rukovodstvo-po-obespecheniyu-dostupnosti-veb-kontenta>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
4. Digital Report, "Uzbekistan: Internet access," available at: <https://digital.report/uzbekistan-dostup-v-internet/>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
5. W3C, "Introduction to Web Accessibility," available at: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/fundamentals/accessibility-intro/#context>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
6. World Bank, "World Bank Document," no additional details available. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
7. "Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Digital Development," available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/5501225#5511167>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
8. DataReportal, "Digital 2024: Uzbekistan," available at: <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2024-uzbekistan>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
9. Digital Report, "Uzbekistan: ICT overview," available at: <https://digital.report/uzbekistan-ikt/>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
10. IT-Park Uzbekistan, "Recommendations for ensuring web content accessibility," available at: https://it-park.uz/storage/images/newsimage/%D0%A0%D0%B5%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BC%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B4%D0%B0%D1%86%D0%B8%D0%B8%D0%BF%D0%BE%D0%BE%D0%B1%D0%B5%D1%81%D0%BF%D0%B5%D1%87%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D1%8E%D0%B4%D0%BE%D1%81%D1%82%D1%83%D0%BF%D0%BD%D0%BE%D1%81%D1%82%D0%B8%D0%B2%D0%B5%D0%B1%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BD%D1%82%D0%B5%D0%BD%D1%82%D0%B0_1635775615.pdf. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
11. Gazeta.uz, "Accessibility for people with disabilities: Current situation in Uzbekistan," available at: <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2024/05/15/accessibility/>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
12. Diplomat Magazine, "Uzbekistan on the path of digitalization: Achievements and plans," available at: <https://diplomatmagazine.eu/2022/04/24/uzbekistan-on-the-path-of-digitalization-achievements-and-plans/>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
13. Medium, "Basic principles of web accessibility: Putting the 'P' in POUR," available at: <https://medium.com/prudential-design/basic-principles-of-web-accessibility-putting-the-p-in-pour-18a938a13d8a>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
14. W3C, "Accessibility principles and standards," available at: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/fundamentals/accessibility-principles/#standards>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
15. W3C, "Introduction to Web Accessibility," available at: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/fundamentals/accessibility-intro/>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
16. DataReportal, "Digital 2023: Uzbekistan," available at: <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2023-uzbekistan>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].
17. UzDaily, "The number of internet users in Uzbekistan exceeds 31 million," available at: <https://uzdaily.uz/en/the-number-of-internet-users-in-uzbekistan-exceeds-31-million/>. [Accessed Dec. 26, 2024].

